

UPSCALING FLUID DYNAMICS IN PERMEABLE POROELASTIC MEDIA: SPATIAL AVERAGING AND DYNAMIC CONSTITUTIVE PARAMETERS

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ABSTRACT

A theoretical analysis is presented for viscous-dominated flows in permeable poroelastic materials. Starting with a continuum-based formulation of momentum transfer in a two-phase solid-fluid system at the pore-scale, the method of local spatial averaging with a weight function is implemented in order to establish a set of differential equations that describe the *dynamics* of fluid flow and solid matrix deformation at the coarser (Darcian) scale. The conditions that delimit the domain of validity for a general biphasic model, as well as for two limiting monophasic descriptions, are established through order-of-magnitude analysis. In the special case of a homogeneous medium and under certain other conditions, the derived equations become similar to those which are postulated in biphasic mixture theory and Biot's theory of poroelasticity.

INTRODUCTION

Fluid flow through deformable porous media is a process of paramount importance in diverse applications ranging from the gravity-driven flow of water in aquifers to the interstitial flow of biofluids in mammalian and plant tissues. Several different approaches have been used in the development of mathematical models for this process, including Biot's theory of poroelasticity, the theory of interacting continua, spatial homogenization and averaging methods^[1,2]. In this paper, momentum transfer in a biphasic fluid-solid system is theoretically analyzed with the method of spatial averaging and the analysis follows the general lines established in our previous work on diffusive mass transfer and steady fluid flow in cellular biological media^[3,4].

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the REV concept for a deformable porous medium. On the coarse Darcian scale (K-scale), the porous medium appears as a continuum (π -phase). The fluid (ν -phase) and solid (σ -phase) constituents are only distinguishable on the finer pore-scale, here denoted as the II-scale.

CONCEPT OF THE SPATIAL AVERAGING METHOD

In the context of the spatial averaging method, a *point* on a coarse scale of observation is considered as the centroid of a volume element with suitable resolution at a finer scale (Figure 1). If the volume element is sufficiently large to include all the phases present at the finer scale and much smaller than the extent of the coarse scale, then it is referred to as a representative elementary volume (REV). The general idea is to define a macroscale quantity by averaging the spatial distribution of its microscale counterpart over a REV with the help of an appropriate weight function. This approach was introduced, in a different context, in the averaging methods developed by *Anderson & Jackson*^[5] in their study of momentum transport in fluidized beds, and by *Marle*^[6,7] in his study on transport phenomena in porous media. Further development of this approach was established by *Gray et al.*^[8] and *Quintard & Whitaker*^[9,10]. Specifically, in Marle's formulation, the finer-scale quantity is defined as a generalized function (distribution) over the entire three-dimensional space, and the corresponding spatial-average quantity is defined by the convolution product of the finer-scale distribution with a weight function. Thereafter, upscaled equations are obtained by applying the averaging operator to the microscale equations.

Let $m_w(\mathbf{x})$ denote a normalized, positive function with compact support that coincides with the REV. Further, let the generalized function corresponding to the microscale quantity ψ_α , be denoted by $\bar{\psi}_\alpha$ and, for instance, defined as

$$\bar{\psi}_\alpha = \psi_\alpha H_\alpha + \psi_{\alpha\omega} \delta_{\alpha\omega} \quad (1)$$

where H_α is a (Heaviside) function associated with the α th phase, and $\delta_{\alpha\omega}$ is the surface Dirac delta distribution concentrated on the $\alpha\omega$ -interface^[4]. The *superficial* and *intrinsic* spatial-averages of ψ_α at a macroscale point $\mathbf{x}^K$ are defined as

$$\langle \psi_\alpha \rangle = (m_w * \bar{\psi}_\alpha)(\mathbf{x}^K, t) \quad (2a)$$

$$\varphi_\alpha \langle \psi_\alpha \rangle^\alpha = (m_w * \bar{\psi}_\alpha)(\mathbf{x}^K, t) \quad (2b)$$

respectively. Here, the symbol $*$ denotes convolution product, and φ_α is the volume fraction of the α th phase. The two averages are related as $\langle \psi_\alpha \rangle = \varphi_\alpha \langle \psi_\alpha \rangle^\alpha$. The two main steps involved in the derivation of upscaled equations can be represented in a generic scheme as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_H \{ \psi_\alpha(\mathbf{x}^H, t) \} = \mathcal{F}_H(\mathbf{x}^H, t) &\xrightarrow{\bar{\psi}_\alpha} \bar{\mathcal{T}}_H \{ \bar{\psi}_\alpha(\mathbf{x}^H, t) \} = \bar{\mathcal{F}}_H(\mathbf{x}^H, t) \\ &\xrightarrow{m_w * } \mathcal{T}_K \{ \langle \psi_\alpha \rangle(\mathbf{x}^K, t) \} = \mathcal{F}_K(\mathbf{x}^K, t) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In the first step, the microscale equations are expressed in terms of generalized functions and, thereafter, the convolution product with the weight function is formed. The weight function serves as a mathematical representation of the influence of the measuring process. The practical importance of using a weight function in the spatial averaging method lies in the fact that it allows one to obtain a precise correspondence between the theoretical dependent variables and the corresponding experimentally measured quantities^[11,12]. In addition, the use of weight functions allows one to relate experimental measurements obtained with different techniques, so as to acquire more precise information about the physical system under consideration.

PORE-SCALE EQUATIONS

Three main assumptions are made for the process under consideration at the pore-scale. First, the *continuum hypothesis* is adopted for the fluid (ν -phase) and the solid (σ -phase). Second, the fluid is considered to be incompressible and Newtonian, and the solid linearly elastic; also, both phases are assumed to be isotropic and homogeneous. Third, convective momentum transfer is considered to be negligible as compared to viscous and elastic stresses. On the basis of these

assumptions, the equations that describe momentum transfer for the fluid and solid phases on the $\mathcal{H}$ -scale of observation can be expressed as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \rho_\nu}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_\nu \mathbf{v}_\nu) = 0 \quad \text{in the } \nu\text{-phase} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\rho_\nu \mathbf{v}_\nu)}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_\nu + \rho_\nu \mathbf{g} \quad \text{in the } \nu\text{-phase} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{BC}_{1a}: \mathbf{v}_\nu \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\nu\sigma} = \mathbf{v}_\sigma \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\nu\sigma} \quad \text{at the } \nu\sigma\text{-interface} \quad (6a)$$

$$\text{BC}_{1b}: \mathbb{P}_{\nu\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{v}_\nu = \mathbb{P}_{\nu\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{v}_\sigma \quad \text{at the } \nu\sigma\text{-interface} \quad (6b)$$

$$\text{BC}_2: \boldsymbol{\sigma}_\nu \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\nu\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_\sigma \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\nu\sigma} \quad \text{at the } \nu\sigma\text{-interface} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho_\sigma}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_\sigma \mathbf{v}_\sigma) = 0 \quad \text{in the } \sigma\text{-phase} \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\rho_\sigma \mathbf{v}_\sigma)}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_\sigma + \rho_\sigma \mathbf{g} \quad \text{in the } \sigma\text{-phase} \quad (9)$$

Here, ρ_α is the density of the α th phase, $\mathbf{v}_\alpha$ is the velocity vector of the α th phase, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_\alpha$ is the Cauchy stress tensor of the α th phase ($\alpha = \nu, \sigma$), $\mathbf{g}$ is the gravity acceleration, $\mathbf{n}_{\alpha\omega}$ is the unit vector normal to the $\alpha\omega$ -interface and pointing from the α th phase toward the ω th phase, and $\mathbb{P}_{\alpha\omega}$ is a second order tensor defined as $\mathbb{P}_{\alpha\omega} = \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{n}_{\alpha\omega} \mathbf{n}_{\alpha\omega}$. The action of $\mathbb{P}_{\alpha\omega}$ on a vector gives the projection of that vector on the plane tangential to the $\alpha\omega$ -interface. Equation (6a) expresses the mass balance at the $\nu\sigma$ -interface assuming negligible interphase mass transfer and accumulation of mass on the interface. Equation (6b) expresses the no-slip condition at the $\nu\sigma$ -interface. Combining equations BC_{1a} and BC_{1b} we obtain:

$$\text{BC}_1: \mathbf{v}_\nu = \mathbf{v}_\sigma \quad \text{at the } \nu\sigma\text{-interface} \quad (10)$$

Equation (7) expresses the linear momentum balance on the $\nu\sigma$ -interface considering negligible interfacial tension. The expressions for the stress tensors are

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_\nu = -p_\nu \mathbf{I} + \mu_\nu \left[\nabla \mathbf{v}_\nu + (\nabla \mathbf{v}_\nu)^T \right] \quad (11)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_\sigma = \mu_\sigma \left[\nabla \mathbf{u}_\sigma + (\nabla \mathbf{u}_\sigma)^T \right] + \lambda_\sigma \mathbf{I} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_\sigma \quad (12)$$

where p_ν is the fluid pressure, $\mathbf{u}_\sigma$ is the solid displacement vector, μ_ν is the dynamic viscosity of the ν -phase, μ_σ and λ_σ are the Lamé parameters for the σ -phase.

DARCIAN-SCALE EQUATIONS: GENERAL BIPHASIC MODEL

Application of the spatial averaging operator to the pore-scale equations results in the following set of differential equations, which hold at any point in the π -phase on the $\mathcal{K}$ -scale of observation. The detailed derivation is presented elsewhere^[13].

Mass balance for the α th phase ($\alpha = \nu, \sigma$)

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_\alpha \rho_\alpha}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\varphi_\alpha \rho_\alpha \langle \mathbf{v}_\alpha \rangle^\alpha) = 0 \quad (13)$$

Linear momentum balance for the α th phase ($\alpha = \nu, \sigma$ and $\omega \neq \alpha$)

$$\varphi_\alpha \rho_\alpha \frac{\partial \langle \mathbf{v}_\alpha \rangle^\alpha}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot \langle \boldsymbol{\sigma}_\alpha \rangle + \mathbf{F}_{\alpha\omega \rightarrow \alpha} + \varphi_\alpha \rho_\alpha \mathbf{g} \quad (14)$$

Constitutive equation for the stress tensors

$$\langle \boldsymbol{\sigma}_\nu \rangle = \underbrace{-\varphi_\nu \langle p_\nu \rangle^\nu \mathbf{I}}_{\text{pressure}} + \underbrace{\varphi_\nu \mu_\nu \left[\nabla \langle \mathbf{v}_\nu \rangle^\nu + \left(\nabla \langle \mathbf{v}_\nu \rangle^\nu \right)^T \right]}_{\text{viscous stress}} + \underbrace{\varphi_\nu \mu_\nu \left[\mathbf{H}_{\nu 1}^{(3)} \cdot \Delta \mathbf{v} + \Delta \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{H}_{\nu 2}^{(3)} \right]}_{\text{extra stress caused by the transient configuration of the } \nu\sigma\text{-interface}} \quad (15)$$

$$\langle \boldsymbol{\sigma}_\sigma \rangle = (\varphi_\sigma \mu_\sigma \mathbf{I}^{(4)} + \mathbf{H}_{\sigma 1}^{(4)}) : \langle \mathbf{E}_\sigma \rangle + (\varphi_\sigma \lambda_\sigma \mathbf{I} + \mathbf{H}_{\sigma 2}^{(2)}) \nabla \cdot \langle \mathbf{u}_\sigma \rangle^\sigma + \underbrace{\mathbf{H}_{\sigma 3}^{(3)} \cdot \Delta \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{H}_{\sigma 4}^{(2)} \langle \mathbf{p}_v \rangle^v + \mathbf{H}_{\sigma 5}^{(4)} : \langle \dot{\mathbf{E}}_v \rangle}_{\text{fluid-solid coupled stresses}} \quad (16)$$

Constitutive equation for the interaction force

$$\mathbf{F}_{v\sigma \rightarrow v} = -(\nabla \varphi_v) \cdot \left\{ -\langle p_v \rangle^v \mathbf{I} + \mu_v \left[\nabla \langle \mathbf{v}_v \rangle^v + \left(\nabla \langle \mathbf{v}_v \rangle^v \right)^T \right] \right\} - \mu_v \varphi_v^2 \mathbf{K}_\pi^{-1} \cdot \Delta \mathbf{v} \quad (17)$$

Saturation condition

$$1 = \varphi_v(t) + \varphi_\sigma(t) \quad (18)$$

Equation of change for the fluid volume fraction

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_v}{\partial t} + \langle \mathbf{v}_v \rangle^v \cdot \nabla \varphi_v = \mathbf{h}_v^{(1)} \cdot \Delta \mathbf{v} \quad (19)$$

$$\text{with: } \Delta \mathbf{v} = \langle \mathbf{v}_v \rangle^v - \frac{\partial \langle \mathbf{u}_\sigma \rangle^\sigma}{\partial t}, \quad \langle \dot{\mathbf{E}}_v \rangle = \nabla \langle \mathbf{v}_v \rangle^v + \left(\nabla \langle \mathbf{v}_v \rangle^v \right)^T, \quad \langle \mathbf{E}_\sigma \rangle = \nabla \langle \mathbf{u}_\sigma \rangle^\sigma + \left(\nabla \langle \mathbf{u}_\sigma \rangle^\sigma \right)^T.$$

The dynamic constitutive coefficients $\mathbf{K}_\pi$, $\mathbf{h}_v^{(1)}$, $\mathbf{H}_{v1}^{(3)}$, $\mathbf{H}_{v2}^{(3)}$, etc. can be determined theoretically from the solution of appropriate *closure problems*^[4,13] or, alternatively, by properly fitting theoretical predictions to experimental data. The established set of differential equations is expected to be a good approximation of momentum transfer on the Darcian scale when the following conditions are satisfied:

$$\ell_\alpha^\Pi \ll d_\pi \ll \ell_\pi^K \quad (20a)$$

$$\langle \mathbf{v}_v \rangle^v \ll \frac{\ell_\sigma^\Pi (2\mu_\sigma + \lambda_\sigma)}{\ell_\pi^K \mu_v} \langle \mathbf{u}_\sigma \rangle^\sigma \quad (20b)$$

$$\frac{\varphi_v \mu_v}{\varphi_\sigma (2\mu_\sigma + \lambda_\sigma) \tau_\sigma} \sim \frac{k_\pi}{\varphi_v (\ell_\pi^K)^2} \left(\frac{\tau_{\sigma,c}^2}{\tau_\sigma^2} + 1 \right) \quad (20c)$$

$$\frac{(\ell_v^\Pi)^2}{L_v L_\varphi} \frac{\Delta \varphi_v}{\varphi_v} \ll 1 \quad (20d)$$

The length-scale condition (20a) was used in the course of the analysis to make simplifications, and is readily satisfied for the systems under consideration. The kinematic condition (20b) is necessary to disregard the extra (fluid-solid coupled) stresses in the upscaled stress tensor for the solid (Eq.-16). The dynamic condition (20c) delimits the domain of validity of the biphasic description at the coarser scale. If this condition is not met, then the biphasic model degenerates to a monophasic elastic or viscoelastic model (next section). Finally, the condition (20d) for the variation of porosity practically states that the established equations can be used for *weakly* heterogeneous materials that do not have extremely steep gradients in porosity. Careful examination of Eqs. (13)-(19) shows that if the extra stresses and the spatial variation of the volume fractions are disregarded, then the equations obtained here via volume averaging become similar to those postulated in the biphasic mixture theory and Biot's theory of poroelasticity.

MONOPHASIC MODELS BASED ON THE "PERFECT COUPLING HYPOTHESIS"

A special case with particular interest is the *perfect coupling* state, where the two constituents (fluid and solid) move with the same average velocity, that is

$$\langle \mathbf{v}_v \rangle^v = \langle \mathbf{v}_\sigma \rangle^\sigma = \mathbf{v}_\pi \quad (21)$$

The perfect coupling hypothesis is expected to be valid, if the following condition is satisfied

$$\frac{k_\pi}{\varphi_v (\ell_\pi^K)^2} \left(\frac{\tau_{\sigma,c}^2}{\tau_\sigma^2} + 1 \right) \ll \frac{\varphi_v \mu_v}{\varphi_\sigma (2\mu_\sigma + \lambda_\sigma) \tau_\sigma} \quad (22)$$

$$\text{with: } \tau_{\sigma,c} = \sqrt{\frac{\rho_{\sigma} (\ell_{\pi}^K)^2}{(2\mu_{\sigma} + \lambda_{\sigma})}}$$

Here, k_{π} represents a suitable norm of $\mathbf{K}_{\pi}$ (e.g., $k_{\pi} = \text{tr}(\mathbf{K}_{\pi})$). Condition (22) was established using order-of-magnitude analysis for the upscaled momentum balance of the solid constituent^[13]. Three characteristic ratios appear in Eq.-(22). In the right-hand side is the ratio of viscous over elastic stresses, and in the left-hand side is the product of a length ratio with a time ratio. Based upon the perfect coupling hypothesis, we obtain

$$\frac{\partial \rho_{\pi}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_{\pi} \mathbf{v}_{\pi}) = 0 \quad (23)$$

$$\rho_{\pi} \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}_{\pi}}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\pi} + \rho_{\pi} \mathbf{g} \quad (24)$$

where $\rho_{\pi} = \varphi_{\nu} \rho_{\nu} + \varphi_{\sigma} \rho_{\sigma}$ is the apparent density and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\pi} = \langle \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\nu} \rangle + \langle \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\sigma} \rangle$ is the apparent stress tensor of the π -phase. Substitution of the constitutive relations results in the following expression for the apparent stress tensor:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\pi} = - \underbrace{\varphi_{\nu} p_{\pi} \mathbf{I}}_{\text{fluid pressure}} + \underbrace{\varphi_{\sigma} \lambda_{\sigma} \mathbf{I} (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\pi})}_{\text{solid compressibility}} + \underbrace{\left(\varphi_{\sigma} \mu_{\sigma} + \varphi_{\nu} \mu_{\nu} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right) [\nabla \mathbf{u}_{\pi} + (\nabla \mathbf{u}_{\pi})^T]}_{\text{viscoelastic stress}} + \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{extra} \\ \text{stresses} \end{array} \right) \quad (25)$$

where $p_{\pi} = \langle p_{\nu} \rangle^{\nu}$ and $\mathbf{u}_{\pi} = \langle \mathbf{u}_{\sigma} \rangle^{\sigma}$. The following remarks are in order. First, under the perfect coupling hypothesis a monophasic model is obtained for the description of momentum transfer in the poroelastic medium on the Darcian scale. Second, Eqs. (23)-(25) are similar to those proposed by *Harden et al.*^[14,15] for condensed polymer solutions and gels. The constitutive equation for the apparent stress tensor includes a linear viscoelastic term that resembles to the phenomenological *Kelvin-Voigt* model^[16], in which the rheological behavior of the material is modeled by combining a spring and a dashpot in parallel. One important novel feature of our monophasic model is the explicit dependence of the apparent stress tensor on the volume fractions of individual phases and the extra stresses, which are associated with the configuration of the two phases at the pore-scale. Finally, depending on the relative importance of the viscous and elastic contributions in the apparent stress tensor, the monophasic model is either viscoelastic or elastic. Using order-of-magnitude analysis for the third term in the right-hand side of Eq. (25) we obtain the following conditions:

$$\text{If } \frac{\varphi_{\nu} \mu_{\nu}}{\varphi_{\sigma} \mu_{\sigma} \tau_{\sigma}} = \mathbf{O}[1] \quad \text{THEN } \text{viscoelastic behavior} \quad (26a)$$

$$\text{If } \frac{k_{\pi}}{\varphi_{\nu} (\ell_{\pi}^K)^2} \left(\frac{\tau_{\sigma,c}^2}{\tau_{\sigma}^2} + 1 \right) \ll \frac{\varphi_{\nu} \mu_{\nu}}{\varphi_{\sigma} \mu_{\sigma} \tau_{\sigma}} \ll 1 \quad \text{THEN } \text{elastic behavior} \quad (26b)$$

The conditions (20c) and (26), which were established here to delimit the domain of validity of the biphasic and monophasic models, are in agreement with those proposed in *Boutin & Aurialt*^[17] using a different line of analysis for deformable porous media.

In order to examine the practical significance of the conditions given in (20c), (26a), and (26b), we recast them in the following form:

$$\text{If } \frac{N_1}{N_2} \sim p_r \quad \text{THEN biphasic} \quad (27a)$$

$$\text{If } p_r \ll \frac{N_1}{N_2} \ll \frac{1}{N_2} \quad \text{THEN monophasic elastic} \quad (27b)$$

if $\frac{N_1}{N_2} \sim \frac{1}{N_2}$ THEN monophasic viscoelastic (27c)

with: $N_1 = \frac{\varphi_v \mu_v}{\varphi_\sigma \mu_\sigma \tau_\sigma}$, $N_2 = \frac{k_\pi}{\varphi_v (\ell_\pi^K)^2} \left(\frac{\tau_{\sigma,c}^2}{\tau_\sigma^2} + 1 \right)$, $p_r = \frac{2(1-\nu_\sigma)}{(1-2\nu_\sigma)}$,

and: $\nu_\sigma = \frac{\lambda_\sigma}{2(\lambda_\sigma + \mu_\sigma)}$, $\frac{\mu_\sigma}{\lambda_\sigma + 2\mu_\sigma} = \frac{1-2\nu_\sigma}{2(1-\nu_\sigma)}$.

Here, ν_σ is Poisson's ratio for the solid phase, and the symbol $\sim$ denotes same order of magnitude. As for example, consider a sample of a biphasic material undergoing dynamic testing. On the basis of the conditions (27a-c), the observed macroscopic behavior might be described more properly either by a biphasic or a monophasic model depending on certain material and testing parameters. Figure 2 shows representative phase diagrams for the parameter set given in Table 1. Interestingly, a gradual transition is observed from the biphasic poroelastic behavior to the monophasic elastic and viscoelastic behaviors with increasing dynamic viscosity of the fluid phase μ_v , increasing testing frequency f_σ , decreasing Darcy number $k_\pi / (\ell_\pi^K)^2$, and decreasing shear modulus of the solid phase μ_σ .

Figure 2. Representative phase diagrams based on the conditions given in (27a-c) for a biphasic material sample undergoing dynamic testing.

Table 1. Indicative values for the parameter set appearing in the conditions given by (2.83a-c).

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Density of the solid	ρ_σ	1500 kg/m ³
Poisson's ratio for the solid	ν_σ	0.40
Shear modulus of the solid	μ_σ	0.01-10 kPa
Porosity (free-fluid)	φ_v	0.85
Hydraulic permeability	k_π	10 ⁻¹² m ² ; 10 ⁻¹⁵ m ²
Dynamic viscosity of the fluid	μ_v	1 mPa·s; 100 mPa·s
Characteristic length	l_π^K	10 ⁻³ m
Testing frequency	$f_\sigma = 1/\tau_\sigma$	0.1-300 s ⁻¹

CONCLUSION

The problem of flow and deformation for a system of a Newtonian fluid-elastic solid has been studied in considerable extent with up-scaling methods. The first papers on the subject were published in the 80's. The present section can be considered as an extension and generalization of Whitaker's work^[18], where the steady-state problem was studied. The most important novel features of this work are in regard to the extra stresses, the dependence on the volume fractions, and, most importantly, the evolution equation for the volume fractions. Current efforts are focused on the solution of the closure problems for the determination of dynamic constitutive coefficients (higher-order tensors).

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